

On-Line Consumer Comments (E-Wom): A Case Qualitative Analysis on Resort Hotel Consumers

Authors : Yasin Bilim, Alaaddin Başoda

Abstract : The recent growth of internet applications on hospitality and tourism provokes on-line consumer comments and reviews. Many researchers and practitioners have named this enormous potential as “e-WOM (electronic word of mouth)”. Travel comments are important experiential information for the potential travellers. Many researches have been conducted to analyse the effects of e-WOM on hotel consumers. Broadly quantitative methods have been used for analysing online comments. But, a few studies have mentioned about the positive practical aspects of the comments for hotel marketers. The study aims to show different usage and effects of hotel consumers’ comments. As qualitative analysis method, grounded theory, content and discourse analysis, were used. The data based on the 10 resort hotel consumers’ on-line comments. Results show that consumers tend to write comments about service person, rooms, food services and pool in their online space. These indicators can be used by hotel marketers as a marketing information tool.

Keywords : comments, E-WOM, hotel consumer, qualitative

Conference Title : ICBED 2014 : International Conference on Business and Entrepreneurship Development

Conference Location : Copenhagen, Denmark

Conference Dates : June 12-13, 2014